

Synthesis of dihydropyrano[c]chromenes from hydroxycoumarins using Aliquat®336 catalysed condensation in aqueous medium

Amarendra Patra* and Tanusri Mahapatra

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, University College of Science and Technology,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : amarendra.patra@gmail.com Fax : 91-033-23519755

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Abstract : Polyfunctionalised 1*H*,5*H*-/4*H*,5*H*-pyrano[c]chromenes were synthesised by the Aliquat®336 catalysed condensation of 3-hydroxy-/4-hydroxycoumarins, malononitrile and various aromatic aldehydes in aqueous medium under the influence of microwave irradiation. The remarkable advantages of this method are the simple experimental procedure, shorter reaction times, high yield of products and green aspects by avoiding toxic catalyst and solvents.

Keywords : Dihydropyrano[c]chromenes, hydroxycoumarins, Aliquat®336, microwave irradiation.

Introduction

Driven by environmental concerns, the replacement of toxic organic solvents is one of the most important goals in *Green chemistry*, which inevitably avoids solvent emission and/or waste. In recent years, thus much attention has been paid towards using water as solvent for organic reactions. Apart from being cheap, safe and environmentally friendly, this solvent induces enormous rate acceleration and significant simplifications to the reaction procedures.

Dihydropyrano[c]chromenes featuring *O*-containing heterocyclic ring fused on to the coumarin moiety are more potent biologically and pharmacologically active compounds¹. Their biological and pharmacological activities have extended their importance as spasmolytic, diuretic, anticoagulating, anti-cancer and anti-anaphylactic agents, as cognitive enhancers for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases^{2,3}. A number of suitably substituted 2-amino-4*H*-pyrano[c]chromenes can exhibit antihypertensive and anti-ischemic behavior also⁴⁻⁶. In addition some 2-amino-4*H*-pyrano[c]chromenes are also active as photosensitive materials⁷.

Despite their increasing importance, relatively fewer methods have been reported in this context with certain limitations⁸⁻¹². Recently, one-pot conventional synthesis of 4*H*-pyrano[c]chromenes has been reported using TBAB

as catalyst in aqueous media¹³. During our course of work in this field only one paper has been published reporting synthesis and antiviral activity of some suitably substituted 1*H*-dihydropyrano[c]chromenes using reagents and solvents which are not environmentally benign¹⁴. It thus became challenging to the synthetic chemists to make further search for a new catalyst which is suitable in effecting single-pot synthesis of both 1*H*- and 4*H*-pyrano[c]chromenes in environmentally benign way. Aliquat®336 is an efficient eco-friendly, mild phase-transfer catalyst. Previously, several syntheses have been reported in literature using this catalyst¹⁵⁻¹⁷. We have also employed it for the synthesis of cinnamates, 1*H*- and 4*H*-benzochromenes and recently for 1*H*- and 4*H*-benzo[*b*]pyran derivatives as well¹⁸. For further diversifying its catalytic activity, we report herein a single-pot, three-component, eco-friendly synthesis of both 1*H*- and 4*H*-pyrano[c]chromenes using Aliquat®336 in aqueous media under microwave irradiation (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

The reaction is simple and straightforward. In a general experimental procedure, the three-component reaction was carried out by mixing various aromatic aldehydes **1**, malononitrile and 3-hydroxy-/4-hydroxycoumarins with Aliquat®336 (15 mol %) in 3 ml of water followed by irradiation under microwave. The resulting

Scheme 1

polyfunctionalised 1*H*,5*H*-/4*H*,5*H*-pyrano[*c*]chromenes **2** and **3** were obtained in good to excellent yield (75–98%) (Table 1).

All the aromatic aldehydes accommodating functional diversity reacted smoothly and equally well under the experimental condition indicating generality of this process. The significant effect of the solvent has been investigated. A comparison of synthetic method using catalyst

in water and in absence of water is drawn in Table 2. The Aliquat®336 (15 mol %) catalysed condensation of benzaldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol) and 3-hydroxycoumarin (1 mmol) in absence of water afforded 75% of **2a** in 22 min whereas the same was obtained in 89% yield in 15 min in presence of catalyst (15 mol %) in 3 ml of water. Thus it can be inferred that catalyst in presence of water shortens the reaction times as well as

Table 1. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 1*H*,5*H*- and 4*H*,5*H*-pyrano[*c*]chromenes using Aliquat®336 in water

Entry	Ar	Products	Time (min)	Yields ^a (%)	M.p. (°C)	
					Found	Reported ^c
1	C ₆ H ₅ (1a)	2a ¹⁴	15	89	274–276	<i>c</i>
2	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ (1b)	2b ¹⁴	12	78	258–260	<i>c</i>
3	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ (1c)	2c ¹⁴	3	98	272–274	<i>c</i>
4	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ (1d)	2d ^b	5	85	230–234	–
5	3-HOC ₆ H ₄ (1e)	2e ¹⁴	8	83	270–272	<i>c</i>
6	2-MeOC ₆ H ₄ (1f)	2f ¹⁴	20	75	280–282	<i>c</i>
7	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄ (1g)	2g ¹⁴	8	83	226–228	<i>c</i>
8	2,4,5-(OMe) ₃ C ₆ H ₂ (1h)	2h ^b	14	81	248–250	–
9	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ C ₆ H ₂ (1i)	2i ^b	10	88	272–274	–
10	4-OH-3-OMeC ₆ H ₃ (1j)	2j ¹⁴	15	87	276–278	<i>c</i>
11	3-OBn-4-OMeC ₆ H ₃ (1k)	2k ^b	14	90	174–176	–
12	4-OBn-3-OMeC ₆ H ₃ (1l)	2l ^b	16	85	170	–
13	2-Br-4,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂ (1m)	2m ^b	18	82	272–274	–
14	2-Br-4,5-(O-CH ₂ -O)C ₆ H ₂ (1n)	2n ^b	20	80	260–262	–
15	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ (1o)	2o ¹⁴	5	95	242–244	<i>c</i>
16	4-OH-3,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂ (1p)	2p ^b	10	76	240–242	–
17	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ (1c)	3a	5	96	260–263	262–264 ⁹
18	3-OHC ₆ H ₄ (1e)	3b ^b	14	91	258–260	–
19	2-MeOC ₆ H ₄ (1f)	3c ^b	18	77	240–242	–
20	2,4,5-(OMe) ₃ C ₆ H ₂ (1h)	3d ^b	15	83	188–190	–
21	4-OBn-3-OMeC ₆ H ₃ (1l)	3e ^b	14	89	198–200	–
22	2-Br-4,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂ (1m)	3f ^b	16	90	230–232	–
23	4-OH-3,5-(OMe) ₂ C ₆ H ₂ (1p)	3g ^b	4	93	220–222	–
24	3-BrC ₆ H ₄ (1q)	3h ^b	12	80	244–246	–

^aIsolated yields; ^bNewly synthesized compounds; ^cFor products, **2a-c**, **2e-g**, **2j** and **2o**, m.p.s were not found in the literature available.

Table 2. Synthesis of 1*H*- and 4*H*-dihydropyrano[*c*]chromene derivative using Aliquat®336 (15 mol %) in water and in absence of water

Products	Time/min ^a	Yield (%) ^b	Time/min ^c	Yield (%) ^b
2a	15	89	22	75
2f	20	75	28	65
2j	15	87	21	77
2n	20	80	27	72
3c	18	77	26	65
3f	16	90	25	78

^aReaction carried out using Aliquat®336 in water.

^bYield of isolated products.

^cReaction carried out using Aliquat®336 in absence of water.

improves the yield of the products through phase-transfer catalysis.

A proposed mechanism is outlined (Scheme 2) to account for the reaction. It is a composite of Knoevenagel condensation and Michael addition followed by cyclisation process and the catalyst assisted both the steps.

Scheme 2

In order to standardize yield of the products to an optimum, we have tested the aforementioned reaction taking 3-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol) and 3-/4-hydroxycoumarin (1 mmol) with different dos-

ages of the catalyst keeping the reaction condition and period of irradiation same. The best results were obtained with a 1 : 1 : 1 : 0.15 mole ratio of aldehyde, malononitrile, 3-hydroxy-/4-hydroxycoumarin and Aliquat®336 (Table 3). A power setting of 720 W appeared to be the best compromise between efficiency and safety.

The recovery and recycling of PTC was then studied. Recycling study was done with benzaldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol), 3-hydroxycoumarin (1 mmol) and Aliquat®336 (15 mol %). After each run, the reaction

Table 3. Standardisation of the amount of Aliquat®336 for the optimization of yield of the product

No. of observations	Amount of catalyst used/mol % (mmol)	Isolated yield ^a of product 2c (3a) (%)
1	5 (0.05)	78 (74)
2	10 (0.10)	90 (87)
3	15 (0.15)	98 (96)
4	20 (0.20)	97 (95)

^aData within parenthesis for isolated yield of product 3a.

mixture was titrated with diethyl ether and after separating the solid by filtration, ether was removed from the filtrate by evaporation on water bath. Aqueous layer contained entire Aliquat®336 and was reused easily for the

next 2–3 runs with little loss in catalytic activity (Table 4).

Table 4. Recycling study

No. of cycles	Amount of catalyst used/mol %	Isolated yield of product 2a (%)
1	15	89
2	15	88
3	15	87

The structures of the newly synthesized compounds received support from extensive spectroscopic studies. Thus structure of **2l** was established on the following arguments : (a) FT-IR spectrum displayed band at 2190 cm^{-1} that revealed the presence of CN moiety. Appearance of twin bands at 3322 and 3447 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of NH_2 functionality. A band in the region 1735 cm^{-1} corroborated the presence of an α,β -unsaturated lactone carbonyl. (b) In ^1H NMR spectrum a signal at δ 4.94 (1H, s) was assignable to 1-H and the disappearance of signal at δ 6.41 (1H, br. s) confirmed the cyclisation. (c) The noise-decoupled ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **2l** exhibited signals for 27 carbons, two of them as two carbon signals. The DEPT experiment have established fifteen of them as protonated and the remaining twelve as non-protonated. Among the protonated signals, signal for OCH_2 carbon was clearly identified from DEPT experiment at δ 70.1. Signals for OMe and C-4 carbons in turn were ascertained from HSQC experiment. An HSQC experiment allowed identification of the signal of a protonated carbon and the signal of the proton directly linked with it while an HMBC spectrum permitted complete carbon spectroscopic assignments through multiple bond ^{13}C - ^1H correlation. Thus multiple bond correlation of 4-H identified several close-by carbon resonances, viz. C-2, C-3, C-4a, C-10a, C-10b, C-1', C-2', C-6' and CN. Again, from multiple bond correlation of 2'-H and 5'-H signals with carbon resonances for C-3' and C-4' along with multiple bond correlation of 5'-H signal in turn with C-1' and C-3' resonances, C-3' and C-4' resonances were identified at δ 148.6 and 147.9 respectively. Moreover, 7''-H also displayed multiple bond correlation with C-4' and C-1'' resonances. Thus C-4' resonance at δ 147.9 was further verified. Further multiple bond correlation with both the 7-H and 9-H signals identified C-10a resonances at δ

117.1 and correlation with both 8-H and 10-H signals identified C-6a resonances at δ 150.3. The structure of **2l** was further supported by HRMS study. We have incorporated HRMS/microanalytical data for selected products also.

In conclusion, a reliable, rapid and eco-friendly procedure for the synthesis of 1*H*- and 4*H*-pyrano[*c*]chromenes has been developed which includes both the 3-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxycoumarins as starting materials, Aliquat®336 as an inexpensive and nontoxic phase-transfer catalyst and water as green solvent under microwave irradiation. A coupling of Aliquat®336, solvent like water having high dielectric constant and microwave irradiation would greatly benefit synthetic chemists with faster and cleaner reactions from reactants insoluble in water. The advantages of this method also include easy product isolation and catalyst recycling.

Experimental

Melting points (uncorrected) were recorded on a Toshniwal apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT IR-RXI spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ^1H (300 MHz) and ^{13}C (75 MHz) NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AV 300 supercon NMR spectrometer in 5 mm BBO probe in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent, microanalytical data were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 II C, H, N, S analyzer and mass spectra on a Qtof Micro YA 263 spectrometer.

*General procedure for dihydropyrano[*c*]chromenes (2a-p, 3a-h) :*

A mixture of aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol), 3-hydroxycoumarin/4-hydroxycoumarin (1 mmol) and Aliquat®336 (15 mol %) in water (3 ml) was placed inside a BPL-SANYO, 700T domestic microwave oven and was irradiated at 720 W until solid appeared (Table 1). The solid reaction mixture obtained was titrated with minimum volume of diethyl ether. The solid thus separated out was filtered and finally purified by crystallization from dichloromethane and methanol mixture affording products in 75–98% yield. In the ^{13}C NMR data of the products, specific assignments to signals were done via HSQC and HMBC experiments and multiplicity of the signals were determined by DEPT-135 experiment.

Spectral data of newly synthesized compounds :

*3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(4-bromophenyl)-1,5-dihydropyran[2,3-*c*]chromene (2d)* : $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3431 and 3293 (conj. NH₂), 2194 (conj. CN), 1728 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 5.10 (1H, s, 1-H), 7.18 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, 9-H), 7.23 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.33 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 3'-H and 5'-H), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, 7-H), 7.43 (1H, m, 8-H), 7.44 (1H, m, 10-H), 7.47 (2H, t, *J* 8.3 Hz, 2'-H and 6'-H); δ_{C} : 37.0 (¹*J*_{C-H} 137.9 Hz, C-1), 56.6 (²*J*_{C-H} 3.1 Hz, C-2), 116.5 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.7 Hz, ²*J*_{C-H} 7.7 Hz, C-7), 116.9 (C-10a), 119.5 (³*J*_{C-H} 2.6 Hz, CN), 120.7 (²*J*_{C-H} 3.0 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 10.8 Hz, C-4'), 124.8 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.0 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.1 Hz, C-9), 125.1 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.5 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.6 Hz, C-10), 125.8 (C-10b), 129.8 (¹*J*_{C-H} 161.9 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 5.8 Hz, C-3', C-5'), 130.3 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.6 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.5 Hz, C-8), 131.9 (¹*J*_{C-H} 167.7 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 5.4 Hz, C-2', C-6'), 134.4 (³*J*_{C-H} 4.7 Hz, C-4a), 142.5 (³*J*_{C-H} 7.2 Hz, C-1'), 150.3 (³*J*_{C-H} 8.8 Hz, C-6a), 154.0 (C-5), 159.0 (³*J*_{C-H} 3.8 Hz, C-3) (Found : C, 57.5; H, 2.6; N, 6.9. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₁BrN₂O₃ : C, 57.7; H, 2.8; N, 7.1%).

*3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(2,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyran[2,3-*c*]chromene (2h)* : $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3445 and 3304 (conj. NH₂), 2195 (conj. CN), 1724 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.60 (3H, s, 5'-OMe), 3.72 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 3.78 (3H, s, 2'-OMe), 5.14 (1H, s, 1-H), 6.67 (1H, s, 3'-H), 6.78 (1H, s, 6'-H), 7.05 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.21 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 9-H), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, 7-H), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, 10-H), 7.43 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 8-H); δ_{C} : 32.2 (C-1), 55.8 (4'-OMe), 56.0 (C-2), 56.6 (5'-OMe), 57.0 (2'-OMe), 99.1 (C-3'), 113.7 (C-6'), 116.5 (C-7), 117.5 (C-10a), 119.8 (CN), 121.9 (C-1'), 124.6 (C-10), 124.8 (C-9), 126.5 (C-10b), 130.2 (C-8), 134.2 (C-4a), 143.3 (C-5'), 149.4 (C-4'), 150.1 (C-6a), 150.9 (C-2'), 154.2 (C-5), 159.4 (C-3) (Found : C, 64.5; H, 4.4; N, 6.7. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₆ : C, 65.0; H, 4.5; N, 6.9%).

*3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyran[2,3-*c*]chromene (2i)* : $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3462 and 3346 (conj. NH₂), 2194 (conj. CN), 1751 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.69 (6H, s, 3'-OMe and 5'-OMe), 3.57 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 4.98 (1H, s, 1-H), 6.62 (2H, s, 2'-H and 6'-H), 7.13 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.22 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz, 9-H), 7.36 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, 7-H), 7.45 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz, 8-H), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz, 10-H); δ_{C} : 38.0 (¹*J*_{C-H}

135.0 Hz, C-1), 56.1 (¹*J*_{C-H} 144.7 Hz, 3'-OMe, 5'-OMe), 57.1 (C-2), 60.0 (¹*J*_{C-H} 144.1 Hz, 4'-OMe), 105.0 (¹*J*_{C-H} 160.9 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.0 Hz and 5.3 Hz, C-2', C-6'), 116.4 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.4 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.6 Hz, C-7), 117.3 (C-10a), 119.6 (³*J*_{C-H} 2.6 Hz, CN), 124.7 (¹*J*_{C-H} 164.3 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.8 Hz, C-9), 125.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 162.5 Hz, C-10), 126.0 (C-10b), 130.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 164.9 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.5 Hz, C-8), 134.4 (³*J*_{C-H} 4.7 Hz, C-4a), 136.8 (C-4'), 138.8 (³*J*_{C-H} 6.5 Hz, C-1'), 150.3 (C-6a), 153.2 (C-3', C-5'), 154.2 (C-5), 159.0 (C-3); *m/z*, M⁺Na (%); Found : 429.1069 (98). Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₆Na : 429.1063.

*3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(3-benzyloxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyran[2,3-*c*]chromene (2k)* : $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3451 and 3316 (conj. NH₂), 2193 (conj. CN), 1734 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.84 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 4.72 (1H, s, 1-H), 4.96 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 5.08 (1H, d, *J* 17.0 Hz, OCH_a), 5.14 (1H, d, *J* 17.0 Hz, OCH_b), 6.65 (1H, br. s, 2'-H), 6.83 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 5'-H), 6.86 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 6'-H), 7.10 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 9-H), 7.21 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 10-H), 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, 7-H), 7.28–7.30 (5H, m, 2'', 3'', 4'', 5'', 6''-H), 7.41 (1H, dt, *J* 8.4 Hz and 1.3 Hz, 8-H); δ_{C} : 38.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 135.4 Hz, C-1), 55.9 (¹*J*_{C-H} 144.4 Hz, 4'-OMe), 60.9 (²*J*_{C-H} 6.2 Hz, C-2), 71.1 (¹*J*_{C-H} 145.0 Hz, C-7''), 112.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 159.1 Hz, C-5'), 113.6 (¹*J*_{C-H} 155.6 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 5.0 Hz, C-2'), 116.8 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.7 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.6 Hz, C-7, C-10a), 118.5 (³*J*_{C-H} 2.5 Hz, CN), 120.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 159.7 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 6.1 Hz, C-6'), 124.7 (¹*J*_{C-H} 162.5 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.4 Hz, C-10), 124.9 (¹*J*_{C-H} 164.5 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.7 Hz, C-9), 127.1 (¹*J*_{C-H} 160.8 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.7 Hz, C-10b, C-2'', C-6''), 127.8 (¹*J*_{C-H} 160.2 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.1 Hz, C-4''), 128.4 (¹*J*_{C-H} 160.2 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 5.6 Hz, C-3'', C-5''), 130.4 (¹*J*_{C-H} 163.2 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.2 Hz, C-8), 133.7 (³*J*_{C-H} 6.1 Hz, C-1'), 133.8 (³*J*_{C-H} 4.6 Hz, C-4a), 136.7 (²*J*_{C-H} 6.9 Hz, C-1''), 148.4 (C-3'), 149.5 (C-4'), 150.5 (³*J*_{C-H} 8.7 Hz, C-6a), 154.6 (C-5), 157.9 (³*J*_{C-H} 4.1 Hz, C-3) (Found : C, 71.1; H, 4.4; N, 6.0. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₀N₂O₅ : C, 71.6; H, 4.5; N, 6.2%).

*3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(4-benzyloxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyran[2,3-*c*]chromene (2l)* : $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) : 3448 and 3322 (conj. NH₂), 2190 (conj. CN), 1735 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.67 (3H, s, 3'-OMe), 4.94 (1H, s, 1-H), 4.99 (2H, br. s, OCH₂), 6.87 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 5'-H), 6.90 (1H, ill-resolved d, 6'-H),

6.95 (1H, br. s, 2'-H), 7.14 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.17 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 9-H), 7.26 (2H, complex m, 3''-H and 5''-H), 7.29 (1H, complex m, 4''-H), 7.32 (2H, complex m, 2''-H and 6''-H), 7.35 (1H, complex m, 7-H), 7.43 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 8-H), 7.46 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz, 10-H); δ_{C} : 37.3 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 136.8 Hz, C-1), 55.6 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 144.3 Hz, 3'-OMe), 57.3 ($^2J_{\text{C-H}}$ 5.8 Hz, C-2), 70.1 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 145.3 Hz, OCH₂), 112.5 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 159.7 Hz, C-5'), 113.4 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 156.8 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 5.5 Hz, C-2'), 116.4 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 165.7 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 7.6 Hz, C-7), 117.1 (C-10a), 119.7 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 3.6 Hz, CN), 120.3 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 160.3 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.4 Hz, C-6'), 124.7 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 160.5 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 7.8 Hz, C-9), 125.2 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 161.9 Hz, C-10), 126.5 (s, C-10b), 127.9 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 161.0 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.7 Hz, C-4''), 128.0 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 160.3 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.8 Hz, C-2'', C-6''), 128.4 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 165.5 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 7.8 Hz, C-3'', C-5''), 130.2 (ill-resolved, C-8), 134.1 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 4.8 Hz, C-4a), 135.5 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.8 Hz, C-1'), 136.9 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.9 Hz, C-1''), 147.9 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 4.0 Hz, C-4'), 148.6 (C-3'), 150.3 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 9.3 Hz, C-6a), 154.2 (C-5), 158.9 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 3.8 Hz, C-3); *m/z*, M⁺Na (%); Found : 475.1272 (100). Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₀N₂O₅Na : 475.1270.

3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(2-bromo-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyrano[2,3-c]chromene (2m) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3385 and 3326 (conj. NH₂), 2199 (conj. CN), 1740 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} 3.61 (3H, s, 5'-OMe), 3.72 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 5.28 (1H, s, 1-H), 6.74 (1H, s, 3'-H), 7.12 (2H, s, 6'-H), 7.17 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.23 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz, 10-H), 7.24 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, 9-H), 7.36 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 7-H), 7.45 (1H, dt, *J* 8.1 Hz and 1.7 Hz, 8-H); δ_{C} : 37.5 (C-1), 55.7 (C-2), 56.0 (4'-OMe, 5'-OMe), 112.4 (C-2'), 112.9 (C-3'), 115.6 (C-6'), 116.6 (C-7), 117.3 (C-10a), 119.0 (CN), 124.4 (C-9), 124.9 (C-10), 125.0 (C-10b), 130.3 (C-8), 133.2 (C-1'), 134.9 (C-4a), 149.1 (C-5'), 149.3 (C-4'), 150.3 (C-6a), 154.1 (C-5), 158.9 (C-3) (Found : C, 54.8; H, 3.1; N, 5.9. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₅N₂BrO₅ : C, 55.4; H, 3.3; N, 6.15%).

3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(2-bromo-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyrano[2,3-c]chromene (2n) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3425 and 3327 (conj. NH₂), 2191 (conj. CN), 1751 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 5.30 (1H, s, 1-H), 5.95 (1H, s, 4',5'-O-CH_a-O-), 5.99 (1H, s, 4',5'-O-CH_b-O-), 6.92 (1H, s, 3'-H), 7.18 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.19 (1H, m, 6'-H), 7.20 (1H, m, 10-H), 7.24 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, 9-H), 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 7-H), 7.45 (1H, t,

J 7.5 Hz, 8-H); δ_{C} : 37.3 (C-1), 55.7 (C-2), 102.3 (4',5'-O-CH₂-O-), 109.6 (C-3'), 112.1 (C-6'), 112.5 (C-2'), 116.6 (C-7), 117.2 (C-10a), 118.8 (CN), 124.2 (C-9), 124.8 (C-10b), 124.9 (C-10), 130.3 (C-8), 134.9 (C-4a), 135.1 (C-1'), 147.8 (C-5'), 148.3 (C-4'), 150.1 (C-6a), 154.0 (C-5), 158.9 (C-3).

3-Amino-2-cyano-5-oxo-1-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-1,5-dihydropyrano[2,3-c]chromene (2p) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3423 and 3331 (conj. NH₂), 2192 (conj. CN), 1738 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.67 (6H, s, 3'-OMe and 5'-OMe), 4.92 (1H, s, 1-H), 6.57 (2H, s, 2'-H and 6'-H), 7.09 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.20 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz and 0.9 Hz, 9-H), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz and 0.6 Hz, 7-H), 7.44 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz, 8-H), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz, 10-H), 8.33 (1H, br. s, OH); δ_{C} : 37.9 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 129.1 Hz, C-1), 56.3 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 144.3 Hz, 3'-OMe, 5'-OMe), 57.5 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.2 Hz, C-2), 105.4 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 156.8 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 5.6 Hz, C-2', C-6'), 116.4 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 164.9 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 7.4 Hz, C-7), 117.4 (C-10a), 119.8 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 2.6 Hz, CN), 124.7 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 164.1 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 7.7 Hz, C-9), 125.4 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 162.4 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.0 Hz, C-10), 126.4 (C-10b), 130.2 ($^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ 165.5 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 8.6 Hz, C-8), 133.3 ($^2J_{\text{C-H}}$ 2.2 Hz, $^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.8 Hz, C-1'), 134.2 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 4.7 Hz, C-4a), 135.1 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 6.5 Hz, C-4'), 148.3 ($^2J_{\text{C-H}}$ 1.9 Hz, C-3', C-5'), 150.3 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 8.8 Hz, C-6a), 154.3 (C-5), 158.8 ($^3J_{\text{C-H}}$ 3.8 Hz, C-3); *m/z*, M⁺Na(%); Found : 415.0907 (100). Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₆N₂O₆Na : 415.0906.

2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyrano[3,2-c]chromene (3b) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3441 and 3325 (conj. NH₂), 2200 (conj. CN), 1722 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 4.30 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.57 (1H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, 4'-H), 6.59 (1H, br. s, 2'-H), 6.63 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, 6'-H), 7.06 (1H, br. t, *J* 8.1 Hz, 5'-H), 7.36 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 7-H), 7.45 (1H, br. t, *J* 7.8 Hz, 9-H), 7.67 (1H, dt, *J* 7.2 Hz and 1.3 Hz, 8-H), 7.85 (1H, br. d, *J* 7.8 Hz, 10-H), 9.34 (1H, s, OH); δ_{C} : 36.9 (C-4), 58.2 (C-3), 104.3 (C-4a), 113.0 (C-10a), 114.3 (C-2'), 114.4 (C-4'), 116.7 (C-7), 118.3 (C-6'), 119.3 (CN), 122.5 (C-10), 124.8 (C-9), 129.6 (C-5'), 133.0 (C-8), 144.8 (C-1'), 152.2 (C-6a), 153.4 (C-5), 157.5 (C-3'), 158.1 (C-10b), 159.6 (C-2).

2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(2-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyrano[3,2-c]chromene (3c) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3385 and 3304 (conj. NH₂), 2189 (conj. CN), 1709 (conj. lac-

tone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.67 (3H, s, 2'-OMe), 4.67 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.83 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 5'-H), 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 3'-H), 7.06 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, 6'-H), 7.18 (1H, br. t, *J* 7.9 Hz, 4'-H), 7.21 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.40 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 7-H), 7.44 (1H, br. t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 9-H), 7.65 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, 8-H), 7.87 (1H, br. d, *J* 7.7 Hz, 10-H); δ_{C} : 32.3 (¹*J*_{C-H} 139.1 Hz, C-4), 57.1 (²*J*_{C-H} 6.4 Hz, C-3), 103.4 (²*J*_{C-H} 8.3 Hz, C-4a), 111.9 (¹*J*_{C-H} 160.5 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.1 Hz, C-3'), 113.1 (³*J*_{C-H} 4.5 Hz, C-10a), 116.6 (¹*J*_{C-H} 168.1 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.6 Hz, C-7), 119.4 (³*J*_{C-H} 2.6 Hz, CN), 122.4 (¹*J*_{C-H} 167.9 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.1 Hz, C-10), 120.7 (¹*J*_{C-H} 162.1 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.6 Hz, C-5'), 124.7 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.2 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.0 Hz, C-9), 128.6 (¹*J*_{C-H} 161.0 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.5 Hz, C-4'), 129.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 163.5 Hz, ²*J*_{C-H} 5.1 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.2 Hz, C-6'), 130.8 (³*J*_{C-H} 6.0 Hz, C-1'), 132.8 (¹*J*_{C-H} 166.1 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 8.9 Hz, C-8), 152.2 (³*J*_{C-H} 8.2 Hz, C-6a), 154.1 (C-5), 157.3 (C-2'), 158.6 (³*J*_{C-H} 7.9 and 3.8 Hz, C-10b), 159.6 (³*J*_{C-H} 2.6 Hz, C-2); *m/z*, M⁺Na (%); Found : 369.0854 (70). Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₄N₂O₄Na : 369.0851.

*2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(2,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyrano[3,2-*c*]chromene (3d)* : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3399 and 3317 (conj. NH₂), 2191 (conj. CN), 1709 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.60 (3H, s, 5'-OMe), 3.63 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 3.72 (3H, s, 2'-OMe), 4.54 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.62 (1H, s, 3'-H), 6.66 (1H, s, 6'-H), 7.17 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, 7-H), 7.44 (1H, br. t, *J* 7.8 Hz, 9-H), 7.65 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz, 8-H), 7.86 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, 10-H); δ_{C} : 32.4 (C-4), 57.1 (C-3), 99.4 (C-3'), 103.4 (C-4a), 113.2 (C-10a), 114.4 (C-6'), 116.6 (C-7), 119.6 (CN), 122.4 (C-10 and C-1'), 124.7 (C-9), 132.7 (C-8), 142.7 (C-5'), 149.1 (C-4'), 152.0 (C-2'), 152.2 (C-6a), 153.7 (C-5), 158.5 (C-10b), 159.6 (C-2); *m/z*, M⁺Na (%); Found : 429.1066 (85). Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₆Na : 429.1063.

*2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(4-benzyloxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyrano[3,2-*c*]chromene (3e)* : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3397 and 3317 (conj. NH₂), 2191 (conj. CN), 1710 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.69 (3H, s, 3'-OMe), 4.33 (1H, s, 4-H), 4.95 (2H, s, OCH₂), 6.76 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2 Hz and 2.0 Hz, 6'-H), 6.80 (1H, d, *J* 1.9 Hz, 2'-H), 6.87 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 5''-H), 7.16-7.24 (3H, complex m, 3''-H, 4''-H and 5''-H), 7.30 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.32

(2H, complex m, 2''-H and 6''-H), 7.43 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 7-H), 7.46 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, 9-H), 7.68 (1H, dt, *J* 8.7 Hz and 1.6 Hz, 7-H), 7.88 (1H, dd, *J* 7.9 Hz, 10-H); δ_{C} : 36.5 (C-4), 55.7 (3'-OMe), 58.2 (C-3), 70.3 (OCH₂), 104.1 (C-4a), 112.2 (C-5'), 113.1 (C-10a), 113.6 (C-2'), 116.6 (C-7), 119.3 (CN), 120.5 (C-6'), 122.6 (C-10), 124.7 (C-9), 127.8 (C-4'), 128.0 (C-2'' and C-6''), 128.3 (C-3'' and C-5''), 132.9 (C-8), 135.8 (C-1'), 137.0 (C-1''), 147.7 (C-4'), 148.5 (C-3'), 152.2 (C-6a), 153.2 (C-5), 158.0 (C-10b), 159.6 (C-2); *m/z*, M⁺Na (%); Found : 475.1274 (98). Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₀N₂O₅Na : 475.1270.

*2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(2-bromo-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyrano[3,2-*c*]chromene (3f)* : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3445 and 3344 (conj. NH₂), 2191 (conj. CN), 1736 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.61 (3H, s, 5'-OMe), 3.72 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 4.84 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.73 (1H, d, 3'-H), 7.12 (1H, d, 6'-H), 7.32 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 7-H), 7.44 (1H, br. t, *J* 7.9 Hz, 9-H), 7.66 (1H, br. t, *J* 7.8 Hz, 8-H), 7.86 (1H, br. d, *J* 7.6 Hz, 10-H); δ_{C} : 36.7 (C-4), 56.9 (C-3), 102.9 (C-4a), 113.0 (C-10a), 113.2 (C-2'), 113.6 (C-3'), 115.8 (C-6'), 116.6 (C-7), 118.9 (CN), 122.6 (C-10), 124.7 (C-9), 133.0 (C-8), 133.4 (C-1'), 148.6 (C-5'), 148.7 (C-4'), 152.3 (C-6a), 154.0 (C-5), 158.1 (C-10b), 159.4 (C-2); *m/z*, M⁺Na (%); Found : 477.0053 (100, for Br⁷⁹), 479.0049 (90, for Br⁸¹). Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₅BrN₂O₅Na : 477.0062 (for Br⁷⁹), 479.0045 (for Br⁸¹).

*2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydropyrano[3,2-*c*]chromene (3g)* : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3381 and 3319 (conj. NH₂), 2199 (conj. CN), 1713 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_{H} : 3.66 (6H, s, 3'-OMe and 5'-OMe), 4.34 (1H, s, 4-H), 6.44 (2H, s, 2'-H and 6'-H), 7.29 (2H, br. s, NH₂), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 7-H), 7.43 (1H, ill-resolved t, 9-H), 7.65 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 8-H), 7.85 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, 10-H), 8.28 (1H, s, OH); δ_{C} : 37.0 (¹*J*_{C-H} 138.4 Hz, C-4), 56.2 (¹*J*_{C-H} 144.2 Hz, 3'-OMe and 5'-OMe), 58.4 (²*J*_{C-H} 6.1 Hz, C-3), 104.2 (²*J*_{C-H} 8.1 Hz, C-4a), 105.5 (¹*J*_{C-H} 157.0 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 5.3 Hz, C-2' and C-6'), 113.2 (²*J*_{C-H} 4.1 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 5.1 Hz, C-10a), 116.6 (¹*J*_{C-H} 167.7 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.9 Hz, C-7), 119.4 (³*J*_{C-H} 2.6 Hz, CN), 122.6 (¹*J*_{C-H} 164.7 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.6 Hz, C-10), 124.7 (¹*J*_{C-H} 165.2 Hz, ³*J*_{C-H} 7.8 Hz, C-9), 132.9

($^1J_{C-H}$ 165.6 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 8.7 Hz, C-8), 133.5 ($^2J_{C-H}$ 6.0 Hz, C-1'), 135.1 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 6.9 Hz, C-4'), 148.0 (C-3' and C-5'), 152.2 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 8.7 Hz, C-6a), 153.3 (C-5), 158.0 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 3.8 Hz, C-10b), 159.7 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 2.4 Hz, C-2); m/z , M^+Na (%); Found : 415.0905 (80). Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_6Na$: 415.0906.

2-Amino-3-cyano-5-oxo-4-(3-bromophenyl)-4,5-dihydropyranof[3,2-c]chromene (3h) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3394 and 3320 (conj. NH_2), 2200 (conj. CN), 1707 (conj. lactone C=O); δ_H : 4.46 (1H, s, 4-H), 7.24 (1H, ill-resolved d, 4'-H), 7.25 (1H, br. s, 2'-H), 7.38–7.47 (6H, complex m, 7-H, 9-H, 5'-H, 6'-H, NH_2), 7.67 (1H, dt, J 8.4 Hz and 1.4 Hz, 8-H), 7.86 (1H, dd, J 7.9 Hz and 1.1 Hz, 10-H); δ_C : 36.7 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 139.7 Hz, C-4), 57.5 ($^2J_{C-H}$ 6.2 Hz, C-3), 103.3 ($^2J_{C-H}$ 8.1 Hz, C-4a), 113.1 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 4.7 Hz, C-10a), 116.6 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 168.7 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 7.1 Hz, C-7), 119.1 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 2.5 Hz, CN), 121.8 ($^3J_{C-H}$ 6.9 Hz, C-3'), 122.7 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 164.0 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 8.3 Hz, C-10), 124.7 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 165.4 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 7.9 Hz, C-9), 127.0 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 161.0 Hz, $^3J_{C-H}$ 6.9 Hz, C-2'), 130.2 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 167.6 Hz, $^2J_{C-H}$ 4.2 Hz, C-4'), 130.5 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 164.8 Hz, $^2J_{C-H}$ 5.0 Hz, C-5'), 130.8 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 164.1 Hz, C-6'), 133.1 ($^1J_{C-H}$ 164.5 Hz, 3J 8.7 Hz, C-8), 146.1 (C-1'), 152.3 (C-6a), 153.8 (C-5), 158.1 (C-10b), 159.6 (3J 2.4 Hz, C-2); m/z , M^+H (%); Found : 394.9879 (100, for Br^{79}), 397.0006 (70, for Br^{81}). Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{12}N_2O_3Br$: 395.0031 (for Br^{79}), 397.0011 (for Br^{81}). *could be exchangeable.

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